

Preliminary phytochemical, antioxidant, anticancer and antimicrobial activity of *Ipomoea marginata* L. (Morning glory)-A review

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Abstract— The present review was aimed to study enzymatic antioxidants (superoxide dismutase, catalase, polyphenol oxidase), non-enzymatic antioxidants (saponin, flavonoids, ascorbic acid and tannin), and anti-oxidant ability assays (total anti-oxidant, hydroxyl radical scavenging ability, reducing power activity, inhibition of lipid peroxide formation, DPPH scavenging activity and metal chelating assay) in *Ipomoea marginata* leaves and whole plant. The results revealed that *I. marginata* possessed significant enzymatic anti-oxidants activities like superoxide dismutase, catalase, polyphenol oxidase in whole plant of *I. marginata*. The non-enzyme anti-oxidants namely saponin, flavonoids, ascorbic acid and tannin showed maximum activity in leaves while the total phenol in whole plant. The anti-oxidant ability assays such as reducing power activity, DPPH scavenging activity and metal chelating assay were found to be high in whole plant. From the study, it was confirmed that the whole plant of *I. marginata* showed strong antioxidant ability assay. Therefore, *I. marginata* leaves and the whole plant can be used as a potential source of natural antioxidants, anticancer and antimicrobial agents.

Keywords— Phytochemicals, Anticancer, Antimicrobial, Antioxidant activity, Morning glory

I. INTRODUCTION

Since ancient times, medicinal herbs have been used, and present day, their usefulness is steadily growing. Herbs have been known and used since ancient times as herbal plants, medicinal herbs or simply herbs. Worldwide, especially in developing countries, the use of natural products, including medicinal plants, has grown in importance in primary healthcare. Numerous pharmacognostical and pharmacological studies are conducted to discover new drugs or new lead structures to develop novel therapeutic agents for the treatment of human diseases such as cancer and infectious diseases [1]. A large number of people in developing countries still rely on folk medicine for the treatment of major ailments such as infections, malignancies and different forms of inflammations.

Folk medicinal plants have been used in many cancer research studies to discover novel therapeutic agents that do not have the dangerous side effects of folk chemotherapy, and the number of substances classified as phytomedicines has expanded significantly over the past two decades [2-6]. More than 50% of all modern drugs in clinical use are natural [7]. have also been reported to be produced from natural compounds, many of which induce apoptosis in different human cancer cells. Consequently, there is an urgent need to develop drugs they are significantly more effective and less harmful.

Traditionally, the plant juice has been used as a diuretic, hypotensive, deobstruent and antidote to poison. Tubers are used as an alternative, aphrodisiac, diuretic, uterine tonic, antidiabetic. The seeds mixed with milk are taken as an important tonic. In veterinary medicine, ground leaves are used for infected wounds[8]. In Ayurveda, it is the only plant that cures female infertility. It is also believed to have the power to give birth to a male child. Its root is perfect for improving physical strength and also acts as a tonic[9]. Root decoction is taken internal to treat leucorrhoea and urinary /kidney stones[10]. The aim of the present study was to revealed the preliminary phytochemicals, antioxidant capacity, anticancer and antimicrobial activity of *I. marginata*.

Breast Cancer

Breast cancer is the most lethal type of cancer in women for both developed and developing countries[11]. The study of molecular and cellular causes and the development of therapeutic approaches have made some significant progress in recent years, but the survival rate for breast cancer has not changed significantly[12]. The discovery of new antitumor agents is of great importance, since currently available anticancer drugs are often ineffective in treating cancer in normal cells. With over 600 species, *Ipomoea* is

the largest genus in the Convolvulaceae family of flowering plants. The common name comes from the Greek words meaning "similar". This refers to their twinning tendency. Ipomoea is used by people for its high concentration of therapeutic and hallucinogenic chemicals [13].

Consequence in vitro antiproliferative effects of *I. marginata* tuber, leaf extract were observed on MCF-7, and the viability of MCF-7 decreased with the sample concentration[14-20]. The LC50 values for MCF-7 cell lines were 130.4864 µg/ml for leaves and 284.8381 µg/ml for the whole plant. According to the study, the whole plant of *Ipomoea marginata* had the elevated level of activity against MCF-7 (human, breast adenocarcinoma) cell lines. Cell viability is often assessed using metabolic viability-based assays such as MTT. Mohd and Saima, 2020[21] determined the cytotoxicity of extracts from different parts (whole, aerial and root) of *I. marginata* against breast cancer cell lines (MCF-7 and MDA MB-231) using MTT and lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) assessments. The existence of flavonoids, terpenoids, anthocyanins are chemicals responsible for the anti-cancer activity against breast cancer cells [22,23]. The plant *Ipomoea marginata* used in the experiment was also verified. Terpenoids and flavonoids are present in their ethanolic extract, leaves and the overall structure of the plant [24] Silva-Correa et al., 2020[25] evaluated the anti-cancer activity of Ipomoea batatas and found that phenolic compounds and anthocyanins are responsible for the anti-cancer activities.

Antioxidant

Antioxidant capacity assays such as total oxidation, reducing energy activity, hydroxide radical scavenging, and inhibition of lipid peroxide formation, DPPH scavenging and metal chelation were determined in the whole plant and leaves of *I. marginata*. The assays such as total oxidation, hydroxyl radical scavenging and reduction of lipid peroxide formation were occurrence in the leaves of *I. marginata*. The reducing energy activity, DPPH scavenging assay and metal chelation assay were high in the whole plants of *I. marginata*. The quantitative determination of total phenols and flavonoids in dried stem, leaves, flowers of *I. cornea* was done using spectrophotometric methods[26]. Ipomoea species such as *I. batatus* and leaf extract of *I. aquatica* have depicted antioxidant properties [27-34]. Sukita et al., [24] studied the phytochemicals in various extracts of *I. marginata* leaves and whole plants and found carbohydrates, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, resins, steroids, saponins, tannins, terpenoids, protein, cardiac glycoside, reducing sugars, proteins and volatile oils showed the presence of carbohydrates, alkaloids, phenol compounds, flavonoids, steroids, terpenoids, tannins, protein and volatile oils were existence in the leaves of whole plants of *I. marginata* in the leaves of whole plants of *I. marginata*. The antioxidant effect of plant extracts are mainly owing to the presence of phenolic compounds such as flavonoids, phenolic acids, tannins, and phenolic diterpenes. Phenolics are the huge group of phytochemicals and are responsible for most of the antioxidant activity of plants or plant products.

It is now generally accepted that under oxidative stress conditions, reactive oxygen species such as superoxide (O_2^-), hydroxyl (OH^\cdot), and peroxy ($\cdot OOH$, ROO^\cdot) radicals are formed. These reactive oxygen species play a key role in degenerative or pathological processes such as aging, coronary heart disease, cancer, atherosclerosis, Alzheimer's disease, neurodegenerative disorders, cataracts, and inflammation. The use of traditional medicine is widespread, and plants are still a large source of natural antioxidants, which can lead to the development of novel drugs. The most effective way to remove free radicals that cause oxidative stress is through oxidation. A variety of free radical scavenging antioxidants are present in the body, numerous of which are obtained from dietary sources such as vegetables, fruits and tea[27, 30-34].

Antimicrobial activity

The growing desire for novel antimicrobials has prompted many studies to focus on investigating the antimicrobial properties of phytochemicals derived from different plant species[35-41]. One approach to address bacterial resistance is the use of herbal or natural products that contain complex chemical compounds and development of resistance in bacteria. Some herbs used in traditional medicine originated in indigenous cultivation and are commonly referred to by local people by their names[42]. *Ipomea*

batatas is a regularly documented and well-studied botanical specimen of the genus *Ipomoea*. The plant, popularly referred to as sweet potato, is recognized for its significant antimutagenic, antiulcer, antidiabetic, and antioxidant properties[43]. The major bioactive compounds obtained from plants of the genus *Ipomoea* are alkaloids containing indolizidine, alkaloids containing nortropane, alkaloids containing ergoline, phenolic compounds, norisoprenoids, coumarins, diterpenes, isocoumarin, flavonoids, benzenoids, glycolipids, anthocyanins, lignan and triterpene compounds. Researchers report that these secondary metabolites have notable antibacterial properties[44].

Phytochemical Screening

Phytochemicals in various extracts of *Ipomoea marginata* were screened for the existence of alkaloids, flavonoids, phenolic compounds, steroids, resins, tannins, saponins, terpenoids, cardiac glycosides, carbohydrates, sugars, proteins and volatile oils. The depicted of Carbohydrates, steroids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic compounds, terpenoids, protein and volatile oils. *Ipomoea marginata* which can act as a potent antibacterial agent. The methanolic extract of *I. marginata* was subjected to preliminary phytochemical testing to identify the chemical constituents [45-50]. The response to microbial infection by plant secondary metabolites is considered to be one of the factors contributing to the anticancer, antioxidant, antimicrobial properties exhibited by plants.

Conclusion

The potential cytotoxic activity in breast cancer cells is due to phytochemical components such as flavonoids and terpenoids. The presence of flavonoids and terpenoids in *Ipomoea marginata* may contribute to its anticancer activity in breast cancer cell lines MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231. The leaves and the whole plant of *I. marginata* exhibit anti-oxidant and radical scavenging activities and the difference in their antioxidant activities, antimicrobial activity may be owing to the various in phenolic content. Further investigation is needed to prove this, validate it using different cancer models, and identify the active ingredient.

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